

PUBLIC PERCEPTION OF SEAWEED AND ITS APPLICATIONS IN RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT, AND INNOVATION

Percepção pública das algas marinhas e suas aplicações em pesquisa, desenvolvimento e inovação

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Abstract: This study investigated public perceptions of seaweed and its applications, aiming to identify barriers and opportunities for research, development, and innovation related to this resource. An opinion poll conducted with 270 Brazilian participants revealed that, although the health and sustainability benefits of seaweed are widely recognized, there remains a significant gap in consumption and knowledge of the subject. The findings indicate that younger individuals were more inclined to explore algae-based products, while adults and the aged demonstrate lower levels of familiarity. In addition, participants with post-graduate degrees were more motivated to buy these products. Developing products preferred by the surveyed population can support processes in companies and universities. It also allows the Brazilian Navy to integrate these technologies into its strategic objectives, thereby accelerating innovation in defense-related products. This work underscores the importance of the bioeconomy and the role of scientific and technological development, aligning with the goals of the Brazilian Navy's Strategic Plan and promoting the visibility of science, technology, and innovation activities.

Keywords: Algae. Research. Bioeconomy. Innovation. Natural products.

Resumo: Este estudo investigou a percepção pública sobre algas marinhas e suas aplicações, identificando barreiras e oportunidades para pesquisa, desenvolvimento e inovação desse recurso. A pesquisa de opinião, realizada com 270 participantes brasileiros, revelou que, embora os benefícios das algas para a saúde e a sustentabilidade sejam amplamente reconhecidos, há uma lacuna significativa no consumo e conhecimento sobre o tema. Os resultados indicam que jovens se mostraram mais inclinados a explorar produtos à base de algas, enquanto adultos e idosos demonstraram menor familiaridade. Além disso, aqueles com pós-graduação demonstraram maior motivação na aquisição desses produtos. O desenvolvimento de produtos alinhados à preferência do público entrevistado pode fundamentar processos em empresas e universidades, além de oferecer à Marinha do Brasil a oportunidade de integrar essas tecnologias em seus objetivos estratégicos, acelerando a inovação em produtos de defesa. Este trabalho reforça a importância da bioeconomia e do desenvolvimento científico e tecnológico, alinhando-se aos objetivos do Plano Estratégico da Marinha do Brasil e promovendo a visibilidade das atividades de Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação.

Palavras-chave: Algas. Pesquisa. Bioeconomia. Inovação. Bioprodutos.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Based on naval objectives, the Navy's Strategic Plan (*Plano Estratégico da Marinha – PEM*) (BRASIL, 2017) defines its requirements through Strategic Programs aimed at achieving the Brazilian Navy's Future Vision. This system is aligned with best practices in governance and public resource management, contributing to the efficiency of government investments and the development of the Defense sector. Therefore, seven Brazilian Navy (*Marinha Brasileira – MB*) strategic programs were established.

For instance, the Brazilian Navy's Nuclear Program (*Programa Nuclear da Marinha – PNM*), beyond fulfilling its naval objectives, has a multiplier effect on the Navy's technological efforts, materialized by the wide variety of resources that can be developed and manufactured domestically. With the growing need for the sustainable development of Maritime Power, biotechnology research can add value to scientific and technological knowledge production activities in maritime and fluvial spaces while simultaneously fostering technological and industrial capacity for national development. Consequently, pursuing more efficient and sustainable fuels, for example, stimulates innovation and benefits the energy sector and other areas, such as health and agribusiness. The fuel cycle, especially the transition to cleaner and renewable fuels, reduces atmospheric pollutant emissions, thereby improving air quality and public health. The production of biofuels, such as ethanol and biodiesel, can also benefit agriculture by creating demand for

specific crops, including sugarcane, soybean, and microalgae (CAVALCANTE FILHO *et al.*, 2023; SILVA *et al.*, 2023; GAURAV; NEETI; SINGH, 2024) (Figure 1A).

According to the Brazilian Navy's Science, Technology, and Innovation Strategy (*Estratégia de Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação da Marinha do Brasil – EMA-415*), research and development (R&D) projects align with the thematic areas of science, technology, and innovation (STI) and share common characteristics in terms of their application in operational and material sectors (BRASIL, 2020). Although the biodiversity bioprospecting research line, encompassed within the marine biotechnology subarea, is solely associated with the operational environment thematic area, it is noteworthy that due to their diverse biotechnological applications, the marine resources currently studied contribute to other thematic areas such as nuclear and energy, combatant performance, and nuclear, biological, chemical, and radiological defense. Seaweeds, for instance, have been investigated for their potential as sources of bioactive compounds for anti-cancer, antidote, antiviral, and antibiotic biopharmaceuticals, as well as for use in superfoods (FARIA LOPES *et al.*, 2020, 2021, 2023; WAHLSTRÖM *et al.*, 2020; SILVA *et al.*, 2022;

CARDOSO *et al.*, 2024) (Figures 1B-1E).

The biotechnological potential of marine algae is extensively studied in science and technology (S&T). However, limitations persist in the R&D process of biopharmaceuticals or algae-based superfood technologies, mainly regarding public knowledge about their applications (Figures 1D and 1E).

Figure 1. Different applications of algae. (A) Biotechnological application of research, development, and innovation (RD&I) in the cultivation of microalgae using a bioreactor for biofuel production. (B) Formulation of supplements using the nutraceutical biomass of microalgae. (C) Macroalgae as a daily staple in oriental cuisine. Source: Images licensed under public domain via google.com. (D) Bioactive compounds extracted chemically from macroalgae with anti-fouling potential (GAMA *et al.*, 2008) and anti-neoplastic (PETERS *et al.*, 2018) potential, among other biotechnological applications. Source: Image from pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov. (E) RD&I in the use of a macroalgae decellularization process for cultured meat technology. Source: author.

According to Patankar and Vamma (2023), the commercial seaweed market generated a revenue of 10 billion US dollars in 2022 and is projected to reach 12 billion US dollars by 2030. This growth can be attributed to factors such as the increasing demand for healthy foods to maintain overall well-being and health, coupled with the high nutritional value and health benefits of seaweed, the growing use of seaweed in hydrocolloid dressings, and the increasing demand for seaweed across end-use industries such as personal care, pharmaceuticals, agriculture, food and beverages, and animal feed. Despite the growing body of research highlighting the numerous benefits and applications of seaweed, the upward trend in this market, and the shift in consumer behavior toward more “green” products, seaweed and its benefits remain largely unknown to the general public.

Understanding consumer perceptions of seaweed is crucial for universities and companies aiming to effectively explore this emerging market, create new products, improve existing ones, and develop effective communication strategies that align with consumer expectations and demands. Identifying barriers to consumption, such as unfamiliarity, taste preferences, or limited access, is essential for companies and educators to develop strategies to overcome them. At the same time, identifying market opportunities in specific segments with higher receptivity to seaweed can open new business fronts and inspire innovation in products that meet the needs and preferences of these consumers. Kamalanon, Chen and Le (2022) explored factors influencing the purchasing behavior of products considered “green.” The research indicates that many consumers are concerned about environmental issues and are interested in purchasing sustainable products. However, actual sales of “green” products do not align with these expectations. Factors such as a positive attitude toward sustainable products, the belief that individual actions can make a difference, environmental concern, and a company’s green image also influence purchase intent. The study suggests that marketers should focus on strengthening this image and increasing environmental awareness to boost sales of sustainable products.

The development of seaweed-based products by companies and universities meets the growing demand for sustainable solutions in the civilian market and offers significant potential for MB. By fostering research and innovation, the Navy can leverage emerging technologies to achieve its strategic objectives. This collaborative effort can accelerate applied research and

innovation in defense products, raising them to levels of technological maturity that meet the operational interests of the Navy. Thus, integrating seaweed biotechnology knowledge strengthens the national bioeconomy and contributes to advancing naval technological capabilities, aligning with the goals set out in PEM and promoting the country’s maritime sovereignty and security. In light of the above, this study used a public opinion survey on seaweed and its applications as a key tool to identify potential consumers’ perceptions of seaweed products.

2. OBJECTIVE

To identify the needs of a diverse target audience and assess their perception of the term “seaweed,” guiding strategic and innovative decisions involving the bioeconomy and national scientific and technological development.

3. METHODOLOGY

The opinion poll was conducted in 2021 and obtained 270 responses. The proposal was carried out at the beginning of the R&D project to understand public perception, suggested applications, current knowledge, needs, and possibilities for innovation. A diverse target audience was selected, consisting of Brazilian adults over 18 years of age with internet access to fill out the Google form (https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1RLVWRTkySQhLZI8b_gqjkRpED7B03k-Fhlax4XPdZfIQ/edit#responses) shared via the authors’ personal Instagram profiles, who made the link available to their personal and professional networks. The form contained 16 questions addressing topics including age, level of education, food preferences, consumer type, instant perception of the term “seaweed,” perceived benefits, frequency and motivation for consumption, and types of products consumed.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. PROFILE OF THE TARGET AUDIENCE

A total of 270 responses from adults aged 18 years old and older were analyzed. The age groups 18-24 and over 65 constituted a minority (6.7%), while those aged 36-45 accounted

questions regarding recent purchases or the lack thereof and the motivation for such purchases based on an understanding of their benefits. However, Figure 3 demonstrates that, across all age group, a disparity exists: the percentage of individuals who recently purchased seaweed-based products is lower than the percentage of those who believe in their benefits.

4.4. ROLE IN HOUSEHOLD DECISION- MAKING AND PREFERENCES FOR ALGAE PRODUCTS

The data demonstrated that among the 62% of respondents who purchased seaweed-based products, 77% perceive health and sustainability benefits. A similar perception (60%) was observed among the 16% who did not purchase such products. Of the respondents who identified as direct consumers of seaweed products, depending on the product type, 22% reported this role. Among them, 79% cited the benefits of these products, primarily for human health and environmental sustainability, as their motivation for purchase (Figure 4A). The word cloud analysis indicated that the majority (80%) of consumed products were related to oriental food, followed by supplementation (10%) such as *Spirulina* and *Chlorella*, presenting an interest in products derived from classic marine biotechnology. The mention of recent purchases of cosmetics and

hygiene products complemented the profile of the every-day consumer (10%) regarding preferences for products and applications of algae in food, supplementation, and cosmetics (Figure 4B).

On the other hand, although 93% of respondents were not vegans or vegetarians, their recent purchases over the last 2 months (44%) and motivations for buying such products (56%) were comparable to those of the minority (7%) who identified as vegan or vegetarian.

Figure 4. Decision-making in the purchase of algae-based products. (A) Percentage of responses from interviewed consumers indicating those with purchasing power, those without purchasing power and those involved in deciding to buy a specific seaweed product. (B) Distribution of the main types of products previously purchased by the interviewees.

Figure 3. Familiarity with algae-based products among different age groups. Familiarity was assessed based on responses to three questions: recent purchase within the past two months, motivation to buy, and belief in the benefits of algae. The 270 answers were normalized to percentage values and characterized into three groups: young individuals (18 to 35 years old), adults (36 to 55 years old), and the aged (56 years old or more).

4.5. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LEVEL OF EDUCATION AND KNOWLEDGE OF ALGAE AND THEIR BENEFITS

The responses showed a relevant difference between post-graduate consumers and those with other education levels regarding their belief in the benefits of algae and their motivation to acquire such products (Figure 5). This finding suggests that only at this level of education is there a greater perception of biotechnological studies involving algae, as well as broader dissemination of related concepts and applications through scientific literature routinely accessed by these master's and doctoral students. On the other hand, other target groups, while expressing interest, demonstrated lower motivation to acquire seaweed-based products, potentially due to limited access to detailed information about biotechnological applications.

4.6. ASSOCIATION BETWEEN THE TYPE OF ALGAE-BASED PRODUCT, AGE GROUP, AND LEVEL OF EDUCATION

The types of algae-based products selected by the interviewees demonstrated varied preference distributions. However, the

overall ranking of the product types mentioned was defined by cosmetics (74%), ointments and dressings (70%), vitamins (69%), culinary use (69%), medications (62%), and veterinary use (42%), which received the lowest percentage of responses. Table 2 shows the distribution of responses across age groups and educational levels for each type of product. Regarding cosmetics, ointments and dressings, vitamins, medications, and culinary or veterinary use, relevant differences were observed between the percentages of young people and adults or the aged and between adults and the aged. These products were most preferred by adults, followed by young people, and lastly by the aged.

When examining preferences according to educational level, important differences were also observed between young people and adults or the aged and between adults and the aged. These products were most preferred by postgraduates, followed by individuals with higher education, and least preferred by those with elementary or secondary education. This corroborates with previous data, suggesting that individuals with higher levels of education often have greater access to information and may participate in research and

Figure 5. Familiarity with algae-based products across education levels. Familiarity was assessed based on responses to three questions: recent purchases within the past two months, motivation to buy, and belief in the benefits of algae. The 270 answers were normalized using percentage values and categorized into primary and secondary education, higher education, and postgraduate studies.

Table 2. Target audience profile and preferences for algae products.

What seaweed products would you purchase?	Age Group			Education level		
	Young Adults (%)	Adults (%)	Aged (%)	Primary and secondary education (%)	Higher education (%)	Postgraduate education (%)
Cosmetics	121 (33)	201 (55)	44 (12)	47 (13)	111 (30)	208 (57)
Ointments&Dressing	57 (30)	107 (56)	27 (14)	24 (13)	57 (30)	110 (58)
Vitamins	61 (33)	100 (54)	24 (13)	22 (12)	53 (29)	110 (60)
Medications	56 (34)	83 (50)	28 (17)	24 (14)	46 (28)	97 (58)
Culinary use	65 (35)	98 (52)	24 (13)	24 (13)	51 (27)	112 (60)
Veterinary use	48 (42)	52 (46)	14 (12)	15 (13)	36 (32)	63 (55)

development to the innovation of such products, reflecting in the decision-making process in their acquisition.

Finally, only 37% of those interviewed provided their contact information for further engagement and interest in the survey. Among these respondents, 33% were young adults, 47% were adults, and 20% were aged.

5. CONCLUSION

The survey on the perception of Brazilian adults regarding their knowledge and familiarity with seaweed has the

potential to benefit MB by providing data that will boost research into the development of bioproducts from seaweed, with applications of direct interest to Defense. The survey could guide initiatives to explore the use of algae in areas such as biopharmaceuticals, biofuels, and biomaterials, contributing to a reduction in technological dependence and the creation of innovative solutions tailored to the Navy's specific needs. In addition, the data can support partnerships with academic and industrial sectors, broadening the scope of projects aimed at the economy of the sea and strengthening the development of technologies adapted to the operational and strategic demands of Defense.

REFERENCES

- BRASIL. Comando da Marinha. *Estratégia de ciência, tecnologia e inovação da Marinha do Brasil*. Brasília: Comando da Marinha, 2017. 103 p.
- BRASIL. Marinha do Brasil. *Plano Estratégico da Marinha (PEM2040)*. Brasília: Marinha do Brasil, 2020. 88 p.
- CARDOSO, N. Q. *et al.* Trends in cell-based seafood: the use of biotechnology for nutrition and sustainability. In: SILVA, L. F. da; GUEDES, D. M.; CRUSÓÉ, J. M. S. F. (org.). *Agricultural sciences unveiled: exploring the dynamics of farming and sustainability*. São Paulo: Atena, 2024. p. 172-194.
- CAVALCANTE FILHO, P. G. *et al.* Socioeconomic impacts of the biodiesel production chain on family agriculture in the Brazilian states of Rio Grande do Sul (RS) and Mato Grosso (MT). *Nova Economia*, v. 33, n. 3, p. 631-658, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0103-6351/7740>
- FARIA LOPES, G. P. *et al.* Marine bioprospecting: from marine sciences to health sciences investigating new bioactive compounds with antineoplastic potential. *Pesquisa Naval*, p. 1-10, 2020.
- FARIA LOPES, G. P. *et al.* In vitro three-dimensional skin development for radiodermatitis, healing, tumorigenesis, and marine bioproduct screening. *Pesquisa Naval*, p. 75-81, 2021.
- FARIA LOPES, G. P. *et al.* Development of superfood technology based on marine natural products. *Pesquisa Naval*, p. 17-25, 2023.
- GAMA, B. A. P. *et al.* Antifouling activity of natural products from Brazilian seaweeds. *Botanica Marina*, v. 51, n. 3, p. 191-201, 2008. <https://doi.org/10.1515/BOT.2008.027>
- GAURAV, K.; NEETI, K.; SINGH, R. Microalgae-based biodiesel production and its challenges and future opportunities: A review. *Green Technologies and Sustainability*, v. 2, n. 1, 100060, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.grets.2023.100060>
- KAMALANON, P.; CHEN, J.-S.; LE, T.-T.-Y. Why do we buy green products? An extended theory of the planned behavior model for green product purchase behavior. *Sustainability*, v. 14, n. 2, p. 689, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14020689>

PATANKAR, N.; VAMMA, J. Commercial seaweed market analysis and segment forecast to 2030. *Horizon Grand View Research*, 2023. Available at: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/horizon/outlook/commercial-seaweed-market-size/global>. Accessed on: Sept. 3, 2024.

PETERS, T. L. *et al.* Target-based screening against eIF4A1 reveals the marine natural product elatol as a novel inhibitor of translation initiation with in vivo antitumor activity. *Clinical Cancer Research*, v. 24, n. 17, p. 4256-4270, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1078-0432.ccr-17-3645>

SILVA, F. R. *et al.* Biodiesel in Brazil: an analysis of production, consumption, and prospects in the energy transition. *Research,*

Society and Development, v. 12, n. 11, e43121143670, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v12i11.43670>

SILVA, I. V. G. E. *et al.* Crosstalk between biological and chemical diversity with cytotoxic and cytostatic effects of *Aphanothece halophytica* in vitro. *Anais da Academia Brasileira de Ciências*, v. 94, supl. 4, p. 1-15, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0001-376520220211585>

WAHLSTRÖM, N. *et al.* Cellulose from the green macroalgae *Ulva lactuca*: isolation, characterization, optotracing, and production of cellulose nanofibrils. *Cellulose*, v. 27, p. 3707-3725, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-020-03029-5>